

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

OAI-PMH API for the Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry

Project Report

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, Grant Agreement #823782.

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Project Number: 823782

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 40 months

OAI-PMH API for the Ethnic and Migrant Minority (EMM) Survey Registry: Project Report

Dissemination Level	PU
Date	02/06/2022
Work Package(s)	WP9 Data Communities
Task	Task 9.2 Ethnic and Migration Studies
Type	Report
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.10

Abstract:

This document provides a short summary of the work, outputs, and findings surrounding the implementation of an OAI-PMH API for the Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ANR	Agence nationale de la recherche
API	Application Programming Interface
CDSP	Centre de données socio-politiques
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CESSDA SaW	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archive - Strengthening and widening
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EMM	Ethnic and migrant minorities
ETHMIGSURVEYDATA	International Ethnic and Immigrant Minorities' Survey Data Network
FAIRETHMIGQUANT	Making Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Data FAIR
FSD	Finish Social Science Data Services
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

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1. Overview

The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry¹ is a free publicly available tool allowing users to learn about existing quantitative surveys undertaken with EMM (sub)populations. It was developed under the umbrella of the H2020 Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project,² in partnership with the COST Action ETHMIGSURVEYDATA³ and the French ANR project FAIRETHMIGQUANT.⁴

The metadata for the surveys included in the EMM Registry uses a custom metadata schema holding over 200 properties.⁵ Mappings have been created by the Centre de données socio-politiques (CDSP) (a French data archive participating in the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)⁶ via PROGEDO) to express the metadata in DDI-Codebook 2.5 compliant XML, which can be downloaded from the EMM Survey Registry as a single XML file⁷ or on a per survey basis.

In order to further facilitate sharing the metadata with other agencies, in particular members of the CESSDA community, SSHOC contracted Integrated Data Management Services⁸ to implement a solution for exposing the EMM Survey Registry content over an OAI-PMH⁹ compliant web service. The Kuha2 platform,¹⁰ initiated by CESSDA SaW¹¹ and now under an Open Source project led by the Finish Social Science Data Services (FSD),¹² was identified as the preferred solution.

It was agreed for the solution to be deployed and hosted by the same company currently hosting the EMM Survey Registry.

Project planning and preparation were discussed over the January-February 2022 period, and work was completed in March and April 2022.

¹Landing page of the EMM Survey Registry: <https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/emmregistry/> [31 May 2022]

²SSHOC's website: <https://sshopencloud.eu/> [31 May 2022]

³COST Action page for ETHMIGSURVEYDATA: <https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA16111/> [31 May 2022]

⁴ANR webpage about FAIRETHMIGQUANT: <https://anr.fr/Project-ANR-19-DATA-0004> [31 May 2022]

⁵Specifications of the EMM Survey Registry metadata schema: <https://zenodo.org/record/4676947> [31 May 2022]

⁶CESSDA's website: <https://www.cessda.eu/> [31 May 2022]

⁷URL for downloading all the EMM Survey Registry's available metadata in XML format: <https://registry.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/api/xml-surveys/> [31 May 2022]

⁸Integrated Data Management Services' website: <http://www.integrateddatasvc.com/> [31 May 2022]

⁹OAI-PMH website: <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/> [31 May 2022]

¹⁰Kuha2's website: <https://kuha2.readthedocs.io/> [31 May 2022]

¹¹CESSDA SaW's website: <http://cessdasaw.eu/> [31 May 2022]

¹²FSD's website: <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/> [31 May 2022]

2. Tasks and Outputs

About 80 hours of work were necessary to complete the project covering the following tasks:

- Requirement analysis
- Familiarisation with the EMM Survey Registry and underlying DDI
- Development and testing of the Kuha2 Docker containers
- Development and testing of DDI updating and harvesting scripts
- Technical coordination with Kuha2 and DotDesign (hosting company for the EMM Survey Registry)
- Support for deployment and testing in the production environment
- Project management and administration

Two Docker containers were created as outputs from the project:

- A generic base Kuha2 server
- An EMM Survey Registry specific Kuha2 server, extending the base version

Both are publicly accessible through the community standard DockerHub platform:

- <https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/mtna/kuha2>
- <https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/mtna/kuha2-emm>

with underlying build scripts and technical documentation available on GitHub:

- <https://github.com/mtna/kuha2>
- <https://github.com/mtna/kuha2-emm>

The base container is an all-in-one server that includes MongoDB¹³ and all the Kuha2 components, namely the document store, both the OSMH and OAI-PMH repository handlers, and the client. It also comes with an nginx web server that can be used as a proxy to the back-end services. A metadata directory is dedicated to hosting the DDI-XML files that are reindexed on a regular basis using a shell script and the Kuha2 client. The script is scheduled as a Linux CRON job.

The EMM Survey Registry version of the container adds a python script that harvests the DDI-XML files from the main EMM Survey Registry, detects changes (based on a checksum), and updates local DDI files as needed. This process is fully automated and does not require user intervention. The log files should however be regularly consulted to ensure the platform is operating as expected.

¹³ MongoDB's website: <https://www.mongodb.com/> [31 May 2022]

The production version of the server is hosted at <https://oai-pmh.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu> with the OAI-PMH service available under the /oai path. For example:

- Server identification: <https://oai-pmh.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/oai?verb=Identify>
- Changes to the metadata since 2022-05-01: https://oai-pmh.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/oai?verb=ListIdentifiers&metadataPrefix=ddi_c&from=2022-05-01
- Metadata for the survey with the ID ITS042 (Multicultural Democracy and Immigrants' Social Capital in Europe: Participation, Organisational Networks, and Public Policies at the Local Level, Turin): https://oai-pmh.ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=ddi_c&identifier=ITS042

3. Findings

EMM Survey Registry DDI-XML endpoint

It was unclear at the onset of the project how and when the DDI-XML files downloadable through the EMM Survey Registry website were created. After investigation, it appears the DDI is not stored in files but generated on the fly from the underlying MySQL database when a request is made, therefore always exposing the latest registry content.

Kuha2 Collections

The Kuha2 server can index 4 different resources: studies, variables, questions, and study_groups. As variables and equations are not included in the EMM Survey Registry, these have been excluded from indexing. Study groups in Kuha2 map to the <serStmt> DDI element, which in the EMM Survey Registry is used to capture the study year or date. This does not seem to be a good candidate for study groups and the element is in any case not consistently populated (optional). In addition, Kuha2 requires the serStmt element to have a unique identifier (serStmt/@ID attribute), but this does not exist in the EMM Survey Registry's DD mapping, and therefore results in an error while processing. Study groups indexing has therefore been disabled for Kuha2.

Kuha2 DDI Subset

The Kuha2 server only indexes a subset of the DDI elements, which can be seen in the application Python source code in the `kuha_commons/document_store/mappings/ddi.py` file (search for the `_study_maps` function). As a consequence, not all elements of the EMM Survey Registry are available

through the OAI-PMH service. This also implies that some updates made to the EMM Survey Registry will not be reflected through the OAI-PMH service.

Kuha2 Versions

During the project execution, a new major version 1.x of Kuha2 was released. As the newer version was not yet stable and production-ready, a decision was made to launch the API using the operational version 0.x. An upgrade to 1.x should be considered down the road.

4. Conclusion

The project was successful in creating an OAI-PMH API for the EMM Survey Registry. The updating process is fully automated which was an unexpected and welcome outcome. In addition, the release of an open-source all-in-one generic container for Kuha2 may benefit other users or agencies interested in using the platform. Upgrading to version 1.x of Kuha2 and other enhancements could be considered down the road through further work or community contributions to the open-source project.

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